

Teaching of specialized subjects in primary education .

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Abstract: Forms of educational organization mean the activities of teachers and students that are specially organized, in a specified order and in a specific mode. One or another organizational form of teaching is a combination of collective and individual teaching in various forms, different levels of independence of learners in teaching, different levels of teacher guidance of learners to study. described by methods.

Keywords: Formal, informal and virtual forms of education, distance forms of teaching special subjects, forms of teaching special subjects: lecture, practical, seminar, laboratory, independent education.

Of the participants of the educational process (teachers and students) carried out in a certain established order represents the organizational form of professional education. The organizational forms of teaching special subjects are understood as ways of organizing a team of students for educational and production activities, forms of leading these activities, as well as the structure of training sessions. In the process of development of human society, education organizational forms were different. In ancient times, the method of individual teaching was widespread, and because it has certain creative aspects, this method has been preserved until now.

By the Middle Ages, education began to be conducted in small groups. Because this period was considered the period when industrial production was launched. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the Czech pedagogue Ya.A. Komensky theoretically proved the class-lesson system. .In ancient times, the method of individual teaching was widespread, and because it has certain creative aspects, this method has been preserved until now. By the Middle Ages, education began to be conducted in small groups. Because this period was the period when industrial production was launched.

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The class-lesson form of teaching special subjects is an organizational form that ensures the fulfillment of a single didactic task for all groups of students under the same conditions (for example, educational-production workshops, educational-production workshops, educational etc.).

allows students not only to learn how to work with various equipment, tools, devices, but also to learn to develop the results of measurements and observations, and to draw correct scientific conclusions and generalizations. The form of the production process is the clarity of the didactic goal, the unity of educational and educational tasks, the correct selection of educational material, the appropriate selection of teaching models, the independence of students, the organizational accuracy of the lesson, and the provision of safety in student work. includes.

Excursion form is a form of organization of higher education through which students get to know the equipment directly in production conditions and observe the organization of

technological and labor processes. Since the class-lesson system is widely used in educational practice, the class-lesson is considered the main form of educational work in the teaching of special subjects in higher education.

A virtual education system is a web system created by teachers to create and manage online courses. Such e-learning systems are often called "learning management systems" or "virtual learning environments". The system is an instrumental environment for creating an educational website and separate online courses, and the system is based on the theory and practice of using computer networks in education. Currently, the introduction of this system in all higher educational institutions of our Republic, along with increasing the efficiency of knowledge, also serves for independent education. Another important aspect of the use of this system in education is that most of the hours of science taught now correspond to independent education. At the final stage of mastering the subject, a general test can be conducted and knowledge can be assessed. As a result, the system monitors the student's knowledge efficiency in a timely manner. A student can register to use the online e-learning system or use the course as a guest.

Distance education is a special form of education that develops a person's independent thinking, situational assessment, conclusion and prediction skills. Another advantage of distance education is that the student can learn at his/her own time and even without leaving work. It is because of these advantages that this system is now widely used in the world. The goal of distance education is to increase the efficiency of independent work of students based on their programming knowledge, imagination and skills - to teach them to think scientifically, to increase their interest in academic subjects, to deepen their professional knowledge, and to increase their activity during theoretical and practical training. The share of distance education in such activity is large. It is known that the teaching model in distance education (primary model, secondary model, mixed model, consortium, franchise, validation, distant audiences and projects), technologies (case, correspondence education, radio and television, network and mobile education) (lim), categories (synchronous and asynchronous) take the main place.

E-learning (Electronic Learning - abbreviation of visual phrase) - electronic education system, electronic education, distance education, computer education, network education, virtual education, use of information and electronic technologies (lab is a synonym of such terms as teaching.

and multimedia teaching" given by UNESCO experts. It can mean many things, including:

- independent work with electronic materials using a personal computer, mobile phone, DVD, audio-video, radio-television;
- the ability to receive advice from a distant teacher, to communicate remotely;
- creating a distributed community of users (social network) conducting common virtual educational activities;
- timely delivery of electronic educational materials around the clock;

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- standards and specifications for electronic learning materials and technologies, distance learning tools;
- formation and development of the information culture of all organizational heads and groups of departments, as well as their acquisition of information technologies, increasing the efficiency of their usual activities;
- acquiring and distributing innovative pedagogical technologies, transferring them to teachers;
- the possibility of developing educational web objects;
- to get modern knowledge at any point of the world at any time and in any place;
- access to higher education for persons with limited physical capabilities (disabled).

Today, lectures occupy an important place in the educational process of higher education institutions, because improving the knowledge of students depends on modern lectures. The transfer of educational materials and information in the form of lectures is considered the main teaching method in the higher education system, and the level of knowledge and skills acquired by students depends on their basic knowledge and age.

A lecture is considered a generally accepted method of presenting educational material on a specific topic, in which theoretical materials are brought to the attention of learners by a lecturer (teacher) based on a systematic, certain sequence. Usually, "information transfer" in the form of a lecture is one of the most complex methods.

On a specific topic by a speaker to a group of listeners. Usually, in a lecture, the audience of listeners appears as a passive receiver. The lecture is more clearly structured than the oral methods of narrating and explaining. Lectures are usually given on major, important issues of the curriculum. In the lecture, the educational material is presented as a whole and coherently, the system of interconnected concepts and laws is revealed, and internal connections are established between different topics of the course. There will be introductory lectures, review lectures, column lectures and closing lectures. A lecture is longer than a lecture (it usually takes an entire class) and involves students writing (summarizing). Listening to a lecture is more difficult than listening to a speech because it requires more attention.

Practical - laboratory classes are divided into the following types according to the nature of their content and organization. Practical-laboratory exercises can be divided into quantitative (quantity-related) and qualitative (quality-related) activities in terms of their character. Quantitative practical-laboratory exercises are accurate measurements, calculations, related to accounts. Their results are expressed by a certain quantity that reveals the quantitative relationships in the investigated object or phenomena. Examples of quantitative practical-laboratory exercises are: determination of quality indicators of crushed soil; determination of seed consumption in planting machines; adjustment of cultivator working bodies, etc. During qualitative practical-laboratory sessions, students make conclusions, clarify laws, and deepen their knowledge; they develop the necessary skills. Examples of qualitative practical-laboratory activities are: testing of metal elongation; selection of cutters depending on the type of work to be performed; studying the structure of various machines and machines, etc. Practical-laboratory training in special subjects can be conducted frontal and non-frontal.

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In frontal practical-laboratory training, all students in the group perform the same task individually or in small groups on the same type of equipment.

In non-frontal practical-laboratory training, students are divided into small groups and perform various exercises or work on various equipment and devices.

Is an independent institution or department, unit of a scientific institution, ministry, enterprise, educational institution that conducts scientific, educational-production or educational activities. . In higher education institutions, the laboratory is divided into three types: educational laboratory (from some academic subjects) - laboratory exercises are conducted with students; scientific-research laboratory - major scientific and technical research issues are solved in the main disciplines; industry laboratory - urgent issues in a specific branch of production are solved. Only if the material and technical base of teaching in educational institutions is well organized, the possibility of training highly qualified specialists will arise. It is very difficult, and sometimes impossible, to organize a standard educational process that ensures the work of a group of learners under the supervision of a responsible teacher in an educational laboratory with production conditions. For this reason, it is assumed that well-equipped educational laboratories and training areas will be organized both in the educational institution itself and in the enterprises. Learners here acquire the skills to organize the workplace rationally, get acquainted with the mechanisms, equipment, and tools necessary to perform the work, learn the working methods of performing the complex of operations and work in a technological order, the culture of production, o they learn to use the study time wisely, comply with the requirements of safety equipment, production and technological discipline.

Independent education in subjects is important in the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students of higher education institutions . Learning skills, receiving learning material, processing, separating its important aspects, connecting newly acquired knowledge with the previous ones, summarizing learning knowledge, repeating and solving problems by applying them in practice are all independent skills. is acquired in the course of lim. Thus, academic skills are related to all educational activities of students in the independent education process . In the process of students' independent knowledge of science, first of all, independent work skills are required. This skill is formed in the process of independent work with educational materials . In other words, learning skills are acquired by receiving, processing, separating the important aspects of the learning material, connecting the newly acquired knowledge with the previous ones, summarizing the learning knowledge, repeating and solving problems by applying them in practice. .

The concept of "independent education" is defined in pedagogical dictionaries as a type of education acquired through independent study outside of the educational institution. At the same time, the terms "independent education", "self-education", "independent study" are used as synonyms. Based on the results of scientific research, independent education is defined as follows : independent education - theoretical knowledge based on independent mastering of educational material, assignments of different levels of complexity, creative and independent performance of practical tasks in the audience and outside the audience, is a systematic activity aimed at forming practical skills and qualifications.

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